

Android Based Smart Application For Students

¹T. Narasimha Rao, ²D Rajeev Naik

^{1,2}Assistant Professor, Anurag Engineering College, Department of ECE, Telangana, India-508206.
tnarasimharao.ece@anurag.ac.in, drajeevnaik.ece@anurag.ac.in

ABSTRACT:-Abstract - Student attendance system is the system of tracking the attendance of the student on basis of presence in class. Successful industries, schools, universities begin by engaging students and making sure that they will come regularly so the attendance rate become very important. In this paper, a smart student attendance system is designed and implemented based on android operating system. In comparison with other traditional attendance systems, the proposed system provides faster, cheaper and reachable system for online student attendance and generate the attendance report automatically.

Key Words: android, student list, session, instructor, course management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Student attendance system is the system of tracking the attendance of the student on basis of presence in class. Successful industries, schools, universities begin by engaging students and making sure that they will come regularly so the attendance rate become very important.

The attendance is important because students are more likely to succeed in academics when they attend class consistently. It's difficult for the lecturer to build students' skills and progress if a large number of students are frequently absent. Because of the advancement of technology today has immersed itself towards education. The presence of technology has reached its maximum of providing sustainable technology towards quality education through delivery and effective learning and smart devices have become a way of life especially in higher education academic fields be able to develop their system into smart attendance.

II. ANDROID OPERATING SYSTEM

Android is a software platform and operating system for mobile devices, based on the Linux kernel, and developed by Google and later the Open Handset Alliance. It allows developers to write managed code in the Java language, controlling the device via Google-developed Java libraries. There are over 300 million Androids in use and over 850,000 devices activated every day. Android is the one of the most used mobile operating system with a market share of 48% and Over 400,000 applications available in Google play store.

III. ANDROID FEATURES

- ✓ User Interaction: Android Provides beautiful, attractive and comfortable user interaction.
- ✓ Connectivity: Android supports different connectivity technologies like Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, and WiMAX.
- ✓ Messaging: SMS, MMS and android cloud to device messaging framework is available in android operating system.
- ✓ Web browser: Browser present in android operating system depends on web kit in mix with Chrome's V8 JavaScript engine supporting.

- ✓ Java support: Most of the android applications are written in java language but there is an absence of java virtual machine in the platform of that DVM is presented. DVM is specially designed for android and battery powered mobiles.
- ✓ Multitasking: Android supports multi-tasking, which provides flexibility of running from one application to another or running different applications simultaneously.
- ✓ Hardware Support: Android supports video or still cameras, touchscreens, GPS, accelerometers, gyroscopes, magnetometers, proximity and pressure sensors, thermometers.

IV. PROPOSED STUDENT ATTENDANCE SYSTEM

4.1 System Tools:

Android Studio has been used as a development environment. Java, PHP and HTML have been used as programming and scripting languages. While, MySQL has been used as a Database management system. WAMP server has been used as a localhost. And CSS as a script for finetuning the screens appearance.

4.2 System Database

Database of the proposed system consists of five tables: users, students, courses, departments and attendance logs. Figure (1) shows the schema of these relational database.

Fig-1:DatabaseSchema

4.3 SystemUsers:

There are three types of system users: Administrator, Reporter and Instructor. Any user who wants to use the attendance system must get user name and password which admin grants it. Attendance system consists from three parts, first part is admin session, which can login to system and edit on all database tables. The second part is instructor session, which login to system for marking attendance and third part is reporter session that also login to system to show attendance and report all the set tasks.

The homepage of the system is the login page. When user opens the system login page, it will prompt, as shown in Figure(2), It involves three input types: Text fields, button and labels. Two text fields for username and password.

Fig-2:LoginPage

A. Administrator Session

After entering the user name and password, the system will redirect the admin into the "Dashboard" page. It contains buttons for Department, Courses, Users, students and logout as shown in figure (3). These buttons are used for adding, deleting and editing; department, course, student and user respectively. The proposed system suppose that current academic system consists of four classes, and two semesters. Figures (4), (5) ,(6) and figure (7) shows managing these sections.

Fig-3:AdminDashboard

Dashboard New Course Logout

Courses List

#	Dep./Course	Class/Sem.	Hours	Edit	Delete
1	Communication & Information / Internet programming	1 / 2	2	Edit	Delete
2	Communication & Information / transmission line	2 / 1	3	Edit	Delete
3	Communication & Information / computer-network	2 / 2	3	Edit	Delete

Fig-4: Course Management Page

Dashboard New User Logout

Users List

#	Full Name	Username	Edit	Delete
1	Administrator	admin	Edit	Delete
2	Instructor	instructor	Edit	Delete
3	Reporter	reporter	Edit	Delete
4	Dr. hikmat	Dr.hikmat	Edit	Delete
5	Dr. Sami hassan	Sami hassan	Edit	Delete
6	Dr. ammar dawood	ammar dawood	Edit	Delete

Fig-5: User Management Page

Dashboard New Department Logout

Departments List

#	Department Name	Edit	Delete
1	Netwroks	Edit	Delete
2	Systems	Edit	Delete

Fig -6: Departments Management Page

Fig-7: Students Management Page

B. Instructor Session

For taking the students attendance for particular department and class, instructor must be logged in the system. After submitting the username and password of the instructor, the system will redirect that instructor to "take attendance" page as shown in figure (8). After selecting a department, class, semester, and the current course, all names of students at that class will appear in student list as shown in figure (9).

Fig -8: Take Attendance Page

Fig -9: Students Attendance Page

C. Reporter session

The third user of the system is the Reporter. This user responsible for extract a report of attendance, for a particular course, as shown in figure (11), or student in specific course, as shown in figure (12).

Name	Attendance	Time
adil yehia	Present	2018-05-17
ahmed radhi	Present	2018-05-17
wrood odia	Absent	2018-05-17
Ali hamza	Absent	2018-05-17
Sami jawad	Present	2018-05-17
adil yehia	Present	2018-05-17
ahmed radhi	Present	2018-05-17
wrood odia	Absent	2018-05-17
Ali hamza	Absent	2018-05-17
Sami jawad	Present	2018-05-17

Fig -11: Student Attendance State

V. CONCLUSION

In term of performance and efficiency, the proposed has provided a convenient method of attendance marking compared to traditional method of attendance system. In addition, it is user friendly system as data manipulation and retrieval can be done via user interface, making it universal attendance system. And adaptive for implement in any educational system.

REFERENCES

- [1] Mohd Heikal Husin, "Smart Attendance Systems Using Technologies", October, 2009.
- [2] Rakhi Joshi, "Android Based Smart Learning and Attendance Management System", June 2015.
- [3] Ganiyu R.A., "Mobile Operating Systems and Application Development Platforms", July 10, 2014.
- [4] "Android Architecture", http://www.tutorialspoint.com/andoid/andoid_architecture.htm.
- [5] Usha Rani & Ramya Krishna, "Overview of Android For User Applications", November 2014.
- [6] Juliana Puentes Giraldo, "programming language definition", 6 May, 2014.
- [7] Gary Sims, "I want to develop Android Apps", January 18, 2016.
- [8] Tim Berners-Lee, "SGML/HTML docs, XBrowser", December 9, 1991.